

Information and Wavelength In Newtonian Mechanics?

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In (1) a particle with rest mass and momentum magnitude p_1 moves from a region with a constant potential V_1 into a region with a constant potential V_2 with the interface being along the x axis. Overall energy is conserved and it is noted that conservation of the x -component is analogous to Snell's law. ((1) goes on to use a variational approach to argue conservation.)

In this note we begin with Newton's idea that momentum changes in the direction of a force and that this force is $-dV/dx$ where $V(x)$ is a conservative potential. For constant V then, forces only arise from discontinuities in potential. We note that for a two dimensional problem (x,y) choosing a starting point of $(x=0, y=Y)$ and changing the incident angle (measured from the y axis, leads to different x values. Thus x is a piece of information in the two dimensional problem. In one dimension (along the x axis), however, momentum is conserved because there is no discontinuity in potential. In this one dimension there is x invariance and x should not be a piece of information. The question becomes: Is there a function in two dimensions that when applied to the two regions of this problem leads to x information disappearing? We consider an ending point $(L-x, -Y)$ where L and Y are constant and note immediately that: $x + L - x = L$ i.e. a constant so that x disappears. Thus if x is multiplied by a constant (namely the x component of p) then the function $A_1 = (p_x)x + (p_y)y$ meets the requirement i.e. $A_1 + A_2$ loses all information about x because of the conservation of (p_x) . As a result one sees the association of p and x which in Newton's theory would normally not be combined. Furthermore if one uses the constraint that $L = 1/(p_x)$ (and drops the $y=Y, -Y$ requirement), then $(p_x)L = 1$ which holds for all p_x values. This is linked to the idea of having one constant (namely 1 here) representing all constant motion as discussed in (2). In this way one may see a characteristic length proportional to $1/p_x$ emerge so that $(p_x)(1/p_x)$ is the same for all constant motion. This characteristic length is the wavelength which appears in experiments.

A second issue we wish to consider is the quadratic form of pp in both nonrelativistic $E = pp/2m + V(x)$ and relativistic $(E-V)(E+V) = pp + m^2c^4$ energy conservation equations. We use the refraction type problem (two constant potentials) together with conservation of $(p_x) = p \sin(\theta)$. We use Newton's idea that force changes momentum in the direction of $-dV/dx$, (p_y) and hence p magnitude must change, but (p_x) must be a constant. Thus one may write: $p_1 p_1 - p_2 p_2 = (p_1 y_1 - p_2 y_2) = C_1$ ((A)). We have used $p_1 x = p_2 x$, but ((A)) leads again to this result so the general result $p_1 p_1 = C_2$ should hold. A similar argument holds relativistically. Thus without integrating one is led to the idea of a quadratic p (i.e. p magnitude p magnitude) as part of a constant equation (because the potential is constant). This we argue is conservation of energy.

Refraction of Particles

In (1) a two dimensional problem of a particle moving in x,y in a region with constant potential V_1 reaches an interface along the x axis before entering a region with constant potential V_2 . The authors note there is conservation of momentum in the x direction and apply a variational principle (Maupertius' least action principle) to also solve the problem. In this note we wish to

consider the idea of information which may appear in two dimensions, but disappear in one dimension.

An Invariant Spatial Variable

We consider the same problem as above with the starting point being $(x=0, x=L)$, the interface being at $y=0$ along the x axis and the ending point being $(L-x, -Y)$ where L and Y are constants. A different x then means a different incident angle as measured from the y axis.

According to Newton's second law momentum changes in a particular direction due to a force in the same direction. This force may be written as $-dV/dx$ where $V(x)$ is a potential if it is conservative. The interface along the x direction ($y=0$) gives rise to a force in the y direction which changes p_1y to p_2y while $p_1x=p_2x$ because there is no change in potential interface in the x direction even though ultimately the particle has a projection moving in the x direction in V_1 and then later a projection in the x direction in V_2 . The issue seems to be one of an impulse hit at the V_1 - V_2 boundary.

This seems to be a situation of information. The medium with constant potential V_1 suggests there is no preferred (x,y) so the particle moves in a straight line. Its momentum does not change. In the second medium the same idea holds except for the fact that something may happen at the interface changing the magnitude of p through a change in p_y . The change in p_y occurs at a specific y point namely $y=0$ which is associated with a medium change (V_1 to V_2). Thus y is a necessary piece of information which applies to all incident angles. There is no special x information which applies to all incident angles (unless one forces the same starting point for all incident angles). One could in principle shift starting points so that all incident rays strike the interface at the same x . Thus x is an invariant and $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$.

In two dimensions one writes:

$$P_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_1 x / \sqrt{x^2 + Y^2} = p_2 \sin(\theta_2) = p_2 (L-x) / \sqrt{Y^2 + (L-x)(L-x)} \quad ((2))$$

with an initial point of: $(0, Y)$ and a final of $\{(L-x), -Y\}$ with Y and L being constants.

Thus x is present as a piece of information in $((2))$ i.e. in two dimensions, but different x values describe different incident angles. In one dimension all information about x should disappear. This begs the question, we argue, that there should be a general function which applied to the two constant potential regions leads to x automatically disappearing. One may include the information that $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$ which is directly linked to the idea of x invariance. Noting that $x+L-x=L$ i.e. a constant one may suggest:

$$A = (p_y)y + (p_x)x \quad ((3)) \text{ for a 2-dimensional problem}$$

$$\text{Then: } A_1 + A_2 = (p_1y)y + (p_2y)y + (p_x)(x+L-x) \quad ((3)) \text{ where } (p_x)L = (p_1x)x + (p_2x)(L-x)$$

All information about x then automatically disappears. Creating $((3))$, however, makes use of the idea of multiplying (p_x) by x i.e. associating momentum and distance as a product which is not

something done in Newtonian mechanics. Such a procedure is only seen in special relativity in which one has the dot product Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$.

Idea of Wavelength

In the previous section we used the idea of creating a function which multiplies components of momentum by their spatial counterparts e.g. $(px)x$. This function together with conservation of momentum for a particular dimension allows for the “disappearance” of the spatial variable in that dimension due to invariance although (px) multiplied by a constant distance may remain i.e. $(px) L$

We argue that one may go one step further and suggest that for a given (px) one may define:

$L=1/(px)$ dropping the $(0,Y)$, $(L,-Y)$ initial/final point requirements and only using $x=0$ as an initial requirement ((4))

In such a case: $(px)L = 1$ for all px values i.e. one constant represents all uniform motion.

Thus a characteristic length proportional to $1/px$ seems to appear such that the function $(px)x$ at $x=1/(px)$ loses all information about a specific px and describes constant motion universally. The question is whether such a constant length appears in nature and the answer is yes due to diffraction/interference results etc.

The Quadratic Form p Magnitude in Energy Conservation

As a second point, we ask whether the above problem of two constant potential regions may lead to the idea of a quadratic momentum magnitude in energy conservation equations?

We begin with the idea of conservation of momentum in the x direction i.e.

$p_1 \sin(\theta_1) = p_2 \sin(\theta_2)$ where p_1, p_2 are magnitudes

The V1-V2 interface changes p_y so that p_{1y} differs from p_{2y} and p_1 from p_2 . If one considers a quadratic form with $(p_1x)=(p_2x)$ then:

$p_1^2 - p_2^2 = (p_{1y})(p_{1y}) - (p_{2y})(p_{2y}) = C_1$ ((5)) where C_1 is a constant linked to V1 and V2

$p_1x=p_2x$ has been used to obtain ((5)), but the remaining equation is also essentially $p_1x=p_2x$ i.e.

$p_1 p_1 [1 - \cos(\theta_1) \cos(\theta_1)] = p_2 p_2 [1 - \cos(\theta_2) \cos(\theta_2)]$ ((6))

((5)), however, is equivalent to:

$p_1 p_1 = C_2$ where C_2 is a function of V1. ((7))

This we argue that ((7)) is the prototype of an energy conservation equation. Furthermore, no nonrelativistic arguments have been made so ((7)) should also apply relativistically. In particular:

$pp = 2m(E-V)$ nonrelativistically and $pp = -m_0c^2 + (E-V)(E-V)$ relativistically.

In both cases the quadratic form of the magnitude of momentum appears.

Conclusion

In conclusion we consider the two dimensional problem of a particle in a constant potential V_1 crossing an interface along the x axis (say at $y=0$) into a region of constant potential V_2 introduced in (1). We argue that the variable x appears in the two dimensional formalism as it is linked to different incident angles if fixed starting and endpoints are chosen namely $(0, Y)$ and $(L-x, -Y)$. In one dimension i.e. the x dimension the variable x should appear due to invariance and this should be linked to conservation in this direction i.e. (px) . Thus we suggest a function: $A = (py)y + (px)x$ that naturally allows for conservation of momentum in a direction to allow for the elimination of the spatial variable in that direction. An overall constant length e.g. L may remain. Thus $A_1 + A_2 = (p_1y)y + (p_2y)y + (p_1x)L$. We argue that one may go one step forward and change the starting point to $x=0$ such that $L=1/px$. The $(p_1x)L = 1$ for any px . This eliminates more information and shows that the idea of $(px)x$ with a special length $x=1/px$ holds for any px . Thus there is in a sense one piece of information namely 1 which may be applied to all constant (px) situations each with their own characteristic length. This characteristic length appears in nature in the form of a wavelength.

We also argue that the quadratic form of the magnitude of p which appears in conservation of energy equations (relativistic and nonrelativistic) may be deduced from this same constant V_1-V_2 problem.

References

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